

Some Studies towards Preparation of *N*-Acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines and *O*-Acylhydroxamic Acids

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A number of *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines (2) have been prepared by alkylation of potassium salt of various hydroxamic acids (1) under different set of reaction conditions. Hydroxamic acids (3) obtained by acidic hydrolysis of potassium salt of hydroxamic acids were subjected to acylation with various acylating agents to give *O*-acylhydroxamic acids (4). The structure assignments of 2 and 4 are based on elemental, ir and nmr spectral data.

HYDROXAMIC acids (3) and their derivatives have recently attracted the attention of chemists because of their widespread uses^{1,2}. However, their chemistry has not been fully explored. In the present communication, attempts have been made to prepare various monoalkyl derivatives (2) of hydroxamic acids by methods other than conventional methods used by various workers³⁻⁵ which require quite a long time. The new method used in this context are (i) solid support synthesis method and (ii) phase transfer catalysis method. These two methods are less time-consuming and the reaction occurred at much lower temperatures.

Alkylation on solid support was achieved by using KF-alumina support in acetonitrile. Under phase transfer catalysis (PTC) conditions the alkylation of potassium salt of hydroxamic acid was achieved by using tetrabutylammonium iodide (TBAI) as phase transfer catalyst in the presence of water-chlorobenzene or water-dichloromethane phase system.

When alkylation was studied on solid support, it was observed that both mono- and dialkyl derivatives were isolated. However, the reaction could be controlled to give preferentially monoalkylated product by controlling the amount of alkyl halide used. Following mechanism has been proposed for the monoalkylation of hydroxamic acids in line with the mechanism given by Miller and coworkers⁶ for alkylation of phenols with alkyl halides.

The beauty of this method lies in the fact that no *N*-alkylated product was isolated. However, in certain cases the alkylation on carbonyl oxygen gave dialkylated product (5)⁸. The formation of dialkylated product can be explained by the fact that hydroxamic acids are known to exist as tautomer (3 and 3a).

3a can react easily with alkyl halide in the presence of KF-Al₂O₃ support to give di-*O*-alkylated product in the following manner,

Since the yield on KF-alumina support was quite good hence no other support was used.

We have applied PTC technique in the synthesis of *N*-acyl-*O*-alkyl hydroxylamines since at present there is relatively very little information on alkylation by PTC method, although this approach has been valuable in a variety of other nucleophilic reactions^{7,8}. Singha and Misra⁹ partially used this technique. In the present communication some modifications have been made to get better yield of the products. Following possible mechanism can be written for alkylation of hydroxamic acid salt by PTC technique,

where, QBr represents the quaternary salt (tetrabutyl ammonium iodide) and R'X the alkylating agent. The remarkable ability of anion associated with quaternary cation in non-polar media to undergo displacement reaction is particularly important.

Since by this process the phase transfer agent brings the transferred species in the reactive form, that is why phase transfer catalysed alkylation proceeds with greater facility. An alternative explanation for enhanced reaction in the presence of phase transfer agent is that a weak complex is formed in which the alkyl halide penetrates into the alkyl group around nitrogen of quaternary compound and such complex may help in the formation of a "push and pull" transition state.

Hydroxamic acids have been reported to undergo a wide variety of reactions. However, very little information is available on their acylation studies¹⁰. In the present paper we present a few *O*-acylhydroxamic acids (4) prepared by acylation of different hydroxamic acids. The importance of these *O*-acylhydroxamic acids lies in the fact that they may possess some pharmacological activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The petroleum ether used throughout had b.p. 60–80°. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc using different solvent mixtures. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 337 spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra (CDCl₃ or CDCl₃+TFA) on a FT-100 instrument using TMS as an internal standard.

Solid support syntheses of *N*-anisoyl-*O*-benzylhydroxylamine: To potassium anisohydroxamate (1.0 g) were added benzyl bromide (1.2 ml) and KF-support (1.5 g) in acetonitrile (25 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10–12 h and the progress of reaction was monitored by the ferric chloride test. After 12 h the ferric chloride colour remained the same. It was then filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated to give a solid product. The product was then treated with anhydrous ether. The insoluble portion was filtered off and the *N*-anisoyl-*O*-benzylhydroxylamine (65%) was obtained from this solution by precipitation with dry petroleum ether. The m.p. was found to be 114° which corresponds well with *N*-anisoyl-*O*-benzylhydroxylamine prepared by other methods. The infrared spectrum showed bands at 3 150 (NH) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=O). The remaining solution of ether-petroleum ether was evaporated to give a solid which was identified as benzyl-*O*-benzylanisohydroxamate (25%), m.p. 70° (Found: C, 75.41; H, 6.32; N, 4.15. C₂₂H₂₁NO₂ calcd. for: C, 75.34; H, 6.05; N, 4.10%). The ir spectrum showed a single band at 1 590 cm⁻¹ (C=N), and the peaks corresponding to NH and C=O groups were absent.

Other *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines prepared by this method are reported in Table 1.

***N*-Anisoyl-*O*-benzylhydroxylamine by PTC method:** Potassium anisohydroxamate (0.3 g) and tetrabutylammonium iodide (0.3 g) were taken in water (10 ml) and benzyl bromide (0.6 ml) in chlorobenzene (15 ml) was then added to it. The reaction mixture was stirred at 70–75° for 14 h. The reaction rate was studied by colour test with ferric chloride, indicating the completion of reaction. The organic layer was then separated from water and washed with water. It was then diluted with ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether was removed at room temperature and then chlorobenzene was removed by vacuum distillation. The resulting solid was taken in ether and recrystallised from ether-petroleum ether, (70%), m.p. 112° (lit.⁹ 114°). The ir spectrum showed bands at 3 150 (NH) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Further, when the compound was mixed with the standard sample of *N*-anisoyl-*O*-benzylhydroxylamine, the melting point showed no depression.

Other *N*-acyl-*O*-alkylhydroxylamines prepared by this method are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF *N*-ACYL-*O*-ALKYLHYDROXYLAMINES (2)

Sl. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	% Yield (%)	
				Method A*	Method B*
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	103–04	55.0	60.0
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl–C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	150–51	65.0	58.0
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O–C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅ OH ₂	112–14	65.0	70.0
4.	C ₆ H ₅	OH ₂ OH=OH ₂	68–4	50	55.0

*A—Solid support method; B—PTC method.

The hydroxamic acids (3): Various hydroxamic acids were prepared by the modified method of Warren and Warren¹¹ and are reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF HYDROXAMIC ACIDS (3)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	% Yield %
1.	C ₆ H ₅	127–28	80.0
2.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ –C ₆ H ₄	162	60.0
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl–C ₆ H ₄	154–55	65.0

***O*-Acyhydroxamic acids. Preparation of *O*-*p*-nitrobenzoylbenzohydroxamic acid:** Benzohydroxamic acid (0.01 mol) was mixed with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) in anhydrous pyridine (25 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 8 h. Upon addition of distilled water (25 ml) to the reaction mixture the resulting precipitate was allowed to settle. The supernatant layer was decanted off. The crude precipitate was dissolved in a minimum amount of absolute ethanol and the solution passed through alumina column. The column was eluted with ethanol. The ethanol fraction thus collected was evaporated to give a

crude product. The product recrystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 158-59 (Found: C, 58.85; H, 3.60; N, 9.85. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2O_5$ calcd. for: C, 58.74; H, 3.49; N, 9.78%). The infrared spectrum showed bands 1640 (C=O of amide), 1765 (C=O of ester), 1520 (NO_2) and 3100 cm^{-1} (NH); δ ($CDCl_3 + TFA$) 7.66 (m, Ar).

The other acylated derivatives were also prepared by the method described above and the results are reported in Table 3.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4

Sl. no.	R	R''	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	C_6H_5	C_6H_5	149-50	78.0
2.	<i>p</i> - $CH_3O-C_6H_4$	C_6H_5	156-57	76.0
3.	C_6H_5	<i>p</i> - $NO_2-C_6H_4$	158-59	60.0
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl- C_6H_4	<i>p</i> -Cl- C_6H_4	175-76	65.0
5.	C_6H_5	<i>p</i> -Cl- C_6H_4	177-78	70.0

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